

Damage Accumulation during Fatigue of Composites

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ABSTRACT

A damage-accumulation approach to the fatigue of composites is outlined. Differential equations for the rate of change of damage are developed, and integrated to give fatigue life. The approach is tested by applying it to published fatigue data. The merits of the method are that it relates closely to physical models of cracking and decohesion, that it can be extended to multiaxial loading, and that, once established, the equations can be integrated for variable load histories to give real service lives for engineering components.

INTRODUCTION

During fatigue loading of a composite material, damage accumulates within it. The damage may have several components: fibre breakage, matrix cracking, decohesion between matrix and fibre, and so-forth. Damage grows with cycling until either the net section stress (allowing for the loss of section caused by the damage) reaches the ultimate strength, or until a critical crack, formed by the aggregation of damage, forms and propagates catastrophically.

The damage can be monitored by measuring other properties of the composite: the moduli, for instance, or the electrical conductivity, or light scattering, or the X-ray absorption, or ultra-sonic attenuation, or the damping coefficient. The moduli are particularly attractive because, being a tensor of fourth rank, they offer the possibility of distinguishing and monitoring different components of damage. In the following sections we outline a differential damage accumulation model, applied, for simplicity, to one component of damage only; the extension to others follows in an obvious way.

GENERAL FORMULATION

Let the fatigue damage be measured by the variable D . At the start of life D is zero unless damage D_i has been introduced during fabrication, or by earlier history. Cyclic loading causes damage to increase from D_i to D_f at which fast fracture occurs either by the aggregation and linking of general damage, or by the propagation of a single crack.

Let the damage depend on cyclic stress amplitude $\Delta\sigma$ and on the current value of D . Then:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = f(\Delta\sigma, D) \quad (1)$$

This can be integrated to give the life, N_f (the number of cycles required to increase D from D_i to D_f):

$$N_f = \int_{D_i}^{D_f} \frac{f}{f(\Delta\sigma, D)} dD \quad (2)$$

The difficulty, of course, is that we do not know the function f . But the damage affects other properties. If, for example, the damage is made up of cracks, then their presence lowers the moduli of the sample, and a modulus can be used to monitor damage. If a relation exists between modulus E and damage D ,

$$E = E_0 g(D) \quad (3)$$

where E_0 is the undamaged modulus, then we have that:

$$\frac{1}{E_0} \frac{dE}{dD} = g'(D) \quad (4)$$

where g' means the derivative of g with respect to D . Substituting into eqn. (1), we find:

$$\frac{1}{E_0} \frac{dE}{dN} = g' \left(g^{-1} \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right) \right) f \left(\Delta\sigma, g^{-1} \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

where g^{-1} is the inverse of g :

$$D = g^{-1} \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right) \quad (6)$$

This equation suggests two alternative approaches to studying damage in composites. First, a damage-accumulation function, $f(\Delta\sigma, D)$, can be guessed or inferred from a model, inserted into eqn. (5), and the result compared with experiment. Alternatively, data can be gathered for E/E_0 as a function of N and, knowing $g(D)$, $f(\Delta\sigma, D)$ can be determined experimentally, using:

$$f(\Delta\sigma, D) = \frac{1}{g' \left(g^{-1} \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right) \right)} \frac{1}{E_0} \frac{dE}{dN} \quad (7)$$

To do so, the right hand side of the equation is evaluated for a range of values of $\Delta\sigma$ at constant E/E_0 , and for a range of E/E_0 at constant $\Delta\sigma$. The function f is determined from a plot of the results.

A SIMPLE EXAMPLE

The Damage Function

Consider a unidirectional composite, loaded parallel to the fibres (Fig. 1). Cyclic loading generates cracks which lie normal to the axis of loading. The cracks reduce the axial modulus E . Define D as:

$$D = \frac{1}{S} \sum_n^n a_n^2$$

where a_n is the length of the n^{th} crack and S is the surface area of the composite. A number of analyses exist for the moduli of cracked solids [1-5]. They are in agreement that, for small D ($D < 0.1$), Young's modulus E_0 for an isotropic solid is reduced by a distribution of cracks to the value of E where:

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = 1 - cD \quad (8)$$

with $c \approx 1.5$.

The form of this result can be obtained by the following approximate argument, which helps in clarifying the definition of D . The elastic strain energy in an uncracked body of volume V and Young's modulus E_0 , held at a constant strain ϵ , is:

$$U_1 = \frac{V E_0 \epsilon^2}{2} \quad (9)$$

If n through-thickness cracks are now inserted into the body, the energy decreases to:

$$U_2 = \frac{V E \epsilon^2}{2} \quad (10)$$

where E is the modulus of the cracked body. The energy difference, $U_1 - U_2$, must be roughly that contained in a volume $\pi a^2 w$ per crack (where $2a$ is the crack length, and w the thickness of the sheet containing it) since this volume is unloaded when the crack forms. Hence, for n cracks in a volume V ,

$$U_1 - U_2 = \int \frac{n \pi a^2 w E_0 \epsilon^2}{2} \quad (11)$$

from which

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = 1 - cD \quad (12)$$

where

$$D = \frac{1}{V} \int \frac{n}{\Gamma} \pi a^2 w \quad (13)$$

and c is a constant of order 1. For contained, penny-shaped cracks, of radius a , the same result holds with:

$$D = \frac{1}{V} \int \frac{n}{\Gamma} \pi a^3 \quad (14)$$

Rigorous treatments (1, 3) give $c = 1.5$.

There appears to be only one treatment of the moduli of anisotropic cracked solids (4). It leads to the result which is well approximated by (8), with a constant c given by:

$$c = \pi \sqrt{\left(\frac{2E_A^2}{E_T} \right) \left| \frac{1}{\sqrt{E_A E_T}} + \frac{1}{2G_A} - \frac{\nu_A}{E_A} \right|^2} \quad (15)$$

where E_A , G_A and ν_A are Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio associated with loading in the axial direction, and E_T is Young's modulus in the transverse direction. Values of c are given in Table 1.

We now use eqn. (8), with appropriate values of c from Table 1. Combining eqns. (1), (7) and (8) gives an expression for the damage function:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = -\frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{1}{E_0} \frac{dE}{dN} \right) \quad (16)$$

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of a composite showing damage

TABLE 1: Variation of c with Material Properties and Lay Up

	E_A (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	G_A (GPa)	ν_A	c
Glass/Epoxy Lamina*	35	5	1.9	0.3	40
Carbon/Epoxy Lamina*	148	9.8	5.3	0.34	72
Kevlar/Epoxy Lamina*	76	5.5	2.1	0.34	76
GFRP [0/90] _S	20	20	1.9	0.07	11
GFRP [±45] _S	11.8	11.8	9.4	0.50	4.7
GFRP [0/±45/90] _S	16	16	5.6	0.36	6.4
CFRP [0/±45/90] _S	62	62	21.7	0.34	6.4

*Typical values

Comparison with Experiment

Stiffness data for plain woven glass-epoxy specimens under constant stress-amplitude loading, $R = -1$, were obtained from Smith [6]; and data for [0/±45/0/±45/90]_S carbon-epoxy specimens under constant stress-amplitude loading, $R = -1$, from Schutz and Gerharz [7]. The typical way in which the axial modulus drops with cycling is illustrated by Fig. 2. The damage function was calculated from each such set of data using eqn. (16). The results, at constant stress amplitude, are plotted as a function of strain amplitude (and thus, via eqn. (8), of D) in Figs. 3, 4 and 5.

The behaviour at constant stress amplitude with $R = -1$, can be broadly divided into two phases. The initial damage growth phase occupies up to 30% of life, and for all cases here, is both stress and strain dependent. It is well described for all but the lowest stress amplitudes by:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = A_1 \exp(\beta_1 \Delta\sigma - \alpha_1 \Delta\epsilon) \tag{17}$$

$$= A_1 \exp\left[\beta_1 \Delta\sigma - \alpha_1 \frac{\Delta\sigma}{E_0(1 - cD)}\right] \tag{18}$$

where A_1 , β_1 , α_1 are constants, readily determined from appropriate plots of the data. In the final phase of damage growth, the damage rate increases with strain amplitude. The data of Smith [6] are well described by:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = A_2 \exp(\alpha_2 \Delta\epsilon) \tag{19}$$

$$= A_2 \exp\left[\alpha_2 \frac{\Delta\sigma}{E_0(1 - cD)}\right] \tag{20}$$

Fig. 2: The data of Smith [6] (22.5° to the weave) for stress amplitudes of 40, 50, 65 and 80 MPa

The data of Schutz and Gerharz [7] show a damage rate in this final phase which has an additional slight stress dependency with:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = A_2 \exp(\alpha_2 \Delta \epsilon - \beta_2 \Delta \sigma) \quad (21)$$

$$= A_2 \exp \left\{ \alpha_2 \frac{\Delta \sigma}{E_0 (1 - cD)} - \beta_2 \Delta \sigma \right\} \quad (22)$$

Data from Smith [6] (45° to the weave) shows an intermediate damage phase with constant damage growth described by:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = A_2 \exp(\alpha_3 \Delta \sigma) \quad (23)$$

Again, the constants, A_2 , α_2 , β_2 and A_3 are readily determined by appropriately replotting the data.

From these equations functions $f(\Delta \sigma, D)$ have been derived for each individual system and plotted against measured dD/dN in Figs. 6, 7 and 8. It can be seen from Figs. 6 and 7 that in the case of the data from Smith the lowest stress loading damage rates are much lower than predicted; though the rate of increase is unchanged.

The data of Smith [6] for fibres at 22.5° to the weave are well described at all but the lowest stresses by:

$$f(\Delta \sigma, D) = 5 \times 10^{-8} e^{0.2\Delta \sigma} e^{-650\Delta \epsilon} + 7 \times 10^{-11} e^{700\Delta \epsilon} \quad (24)$$

Data for fibres at 45° to the weave are described by:

$$f(\Delta \sigma, D) = 8 \times 10^{-10} e^{0.32\Delta \sigma} e^{-515\Delta \epsilon} + 6 \times 10^{-8} e^{225\Delta \epsilon} + 4 \times 10^{-10} e^{0.21\Delta \sigma} \quad (25)$$

Finally, the data of Schutz are described at all stresses by:

$$f(\Delta \sigma, D) = 2 \times 10^{-11} e^{0.08\Delta \sigma} e^{-3200\Delta \epsilon} + 1.5 \times 10^{-12} e^{-0.04\Delta \sigma} e^{3200\Delta \epsilon} \quad (26)$$

where (as before)

$$\Delta \epsilon = \frac{\Delta \sigma}{E} = \frac{\Delta \sigma}{E_0 (1 - cD)} \quad (27)$$

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated that damage accumulation in composites during fatigue can be described by a damage function

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = f(\Delta \sigma, D) .$$

The damage D grows during fatigue from an initial value D_i to a final, critical value of D_f , at which fast fracture takes place. The damage function can be determined by measuring the change of modulus (or probably, of other properties) with cycling; three examples of simple damage functions are given in the text.

The potential of the method lies in its capacity to predict fatigue life under varying load histories, or to predict residual life after a known earlier history. To do so, the damage function must be combined with a failure criterion, which determines the value of D at failure, D_f . (Standard methods of fracture mechanics, for example, can be used to determine the value of D at which catastrophic fast crack growth will occur.) Then the damage function is simply integrated from D_i to this value of D_f , to give the life. Similarly, residual life is calculated by integrating over the load history to give the current value of D , and subtracting those from D_f to give the residual tolerance to damage. The residual life is then obtained from the damage function.

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Fig. 3: The damage rate as a function of strain amplitude for the data of Smith [6] ($22\frac{1}{2}^\circ$ to the weave)

Fig. 4: The damage rate as a function of strain amplitude for the data of Smith [6] (45° to the weave)

Fig. 5: The damage rate as a function of strain amplitude for the data of Schütz and Gerharz [7] $[0_2/\pm 45/0_2/90]_S$

Fig. 6: The damage rate as a function of $f(\Delta\sigma, D)$ as computed from Fig. 3 for the data of Smith [6] (22.5° to the weave)

Fig. 7: The damage rate as a function of $f(\Delta\sigma, D)$ as computed from Fig. 4 for the data of Smith [6] (45° to the weave)

Fig. 8: The damage rate as a function of $f(\Delta\sigma, D)$ as computed by Fig. 5 for the data of Schütz and Gerharz [7]